

Sometimes they come back – *Platypyllus castoris* Ritsema, 1869 (Leiodidae, Coleoptera) new genus and species for the fauna of the Balkan Peninsula

Rostislav Bekchiev¹, Nedko Nedyalkov², Rumyana Kostova³, Nikolay Simov⁴,
Mario Langourov⁵, Ilya Acosta-Pankov⁶

- (1) [Corresponding author] National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, bekchiev@nmnhs.com
- (2) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, nnedko@gmail.com
- (3) Department of Zoology and Anthropology, Faculty of Biology, Sofia University, 8 Dragan Tsankov Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, rkostova@biofac.uni-sofia.bg
- (4) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, simov@nmnhs.com
- (5) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, langourov@nmnhs.com
- (6) National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, ilya.acosta@nmnhs.com

Abstract: The parasite beetle on Eurasian beaver *Platypyllus castoris* is reported for the first time from Bulgaria.

Keywords: beetles, *Castor fiber*, commensalism, Europe, Platypyllinae

Introduction

The species *Castor fiber* Linnaeus, 1758 is known from the territory of Bulgaria based on fossil, subfossil, and subrecent records (Late Pleistocene to the 19th century AD) (Boev & Spassov, 2019). It was considered extirpated in the country; however, it has recently been observed to naturally recolonise Bulgarian territory and establish a stable population (Kodzhabashev et al., 2021). It has been demonstrated that the Bulgarian population belongs to the broader European population, which is gradually recovering in the region (Bobeva et al., 2025).

The first record of *Platypyllus castoris* Ritsema, 1869 on *C. fiber* in Europe dates back to 1884 in the Camargue, France (Neumann et al., 2000; Åhlen et al., 2021). The distribution of *P. castoris* closely follows that of its host, the Eurasian beaver, across

Europe. Over the past century, many European populations of the Eurasian beaver have been successfully re-established through conservation efforts (Duff, 2013), and some recent records of *P. castoris* are associated with these reintroduced populations. The species has been reported from Belgium, Belarus, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, Latvia, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, and (Pushkin, 2014, Löbl & Löbl, 2015;). It has also been recorded in Scotland (Great Britain) (Duff et al, 2013) and Italy (Turillazzi et al., 2023), following beaver reintroductions. Although it is frequently considered an ectoparasite, Yavorskaya et al. (2022) concluded in an in-depth study of its morphology and anatomy that it is more likely to be commensal than a proper parasite, feeding on liquid and possibly emulsified minute skin debris.

Despite growing interest and increasingly intensive studies on the Eurasian beaver in Bulgaria, no specimens of *P. castoris* have been recorded to date, or at least none of the examined individuals have been assessed for the presence of parasites.

Results

On February 24, 2025, two dead beaver specimens (roadkill) were reported in the vicinity of Milevo Village (Plovdiv District), along the Maritsa River. Dr Nedko Nedyalkov (National Museum of Natural History, Sofia, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences – NMNHS) visited the sites and collected the animals along with their associated parasites.

As a result, two specimens of *Platypsyllus castoris* and a few ticks were collected from a freshly dead adult female (19.5 kg) beaver, probably killed early in the morning. The specimens have been deposited in the NMNHS collection. The finding of *P. castoris* represents the first record of both the genus and the species for the fauna of Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula.

Platypsyllus castoris Ritsema, 1869

Fig. 1

Bulgaria, between Milevo and Mirevo villages, on the right bank of the Maritsa River, on dead beaver (roadkill), 24.02.2025, 2 ex., leg. N. Nedyalkov (NMNHS).

Discussion

Although the discovery is new to the Balkans, it can reasonably be assumed that the species was also found in this territory in the past, disappearing along with the extinction of beavers. In this context the finding is not unexpected – given the close association of the species with the beaver and its likely widespread distribution across Europe – it is nevertheless noteworthy, as it adds a new species to the Bulgarian fauna and represents one of the few beetles parasitic on mammals. The discovery provides a basis for more in-depth research into the ecological relationships between the two species.

This is the second species, and last species, of the subfamily Platypsyllinae that can be expected, of the

Fig. 1. *Platypsyllus castoris* (Bulgaria) – size: 2 mm.

subfamily Platypsyllinae recorded in the Balkans, and Bulgaria, after *Leptinus testaceus* P.W.J. Müller, 1817 (Guéorguiev & Bekchiev, 2009). Which is also considered a probable parasite of mammals, or at least closely associated with their nests or dens. This finding highlights how limited our knowledge remains regarding beetles that maintain trophic or habitat relationships with mammals in Bulgaria, and the Balkans.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As members

of the editorial board, Nikolay Simov, Mario Langourov and Ilya Acosta-Pankov withdrew from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Rostislav Bekchiev: conceptualisation, data curation, writing—original draft; Nedko Nedyalkov: methodology, writing—original draft; Romyana Kostova: conceptualisation, visualisation, writing—original draft; Nikolay Simov: project administration, writing—review and editing; Mario Langourov: writing—review and editing; Ilya Acosta-Pankov: writing—review and editing.

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